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Child Abuse in Kaduna Metropolis, Nigeria (2015–2021): Causes, Effects, and Recommendations

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Temitope Adeyemi

Department of Political Science and Defence Studies,
Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna
Kaduna State

Email: topeadeyemi7@gmail.com

Abstract

This study examines Child Abuse in Kaduna Metropolis, Nigeria (2015–2021): Causes, Effects, and Recommendations. Child abuse, including child labour, drug abuse, denial of education, sexual molestation, early marriage, and emotional abuse, is a widespread issue with both immediate and long-term effects on children's well-being and their future roles in society. This study employs a mixed-methods approach, combining both primary data through surveys and interviews and secondary data from literature, including books, journals, and online sources. Guided by the General Strain theory, the research identifies key factors contributing to the rise in child abuse, such as the delinquent behaviours of parents and caregivers and inadequate implementation of the Child Rights Act 2003. This study recommends improved government funding for child protection programs, promotion of awareness campaigns against harmful cultural practices and more rigorous enforcement of child protection laws to address these issues effectively.

Keywords: Child, Child Abuse, Effects, Kaduna.

*There can be no keener revelation of a society's soul than the way in which it treats its children.
(Mandela, 1981)*

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Child Abuse in Kaduna Metropolis, Nigeria (2015–2021): Causes, Effects, and Recommendations**Introduction**

Generally, the international community and the federal governments recognize that children, or an individual child, have rights and these rights specify the minimum standards for their well-being, ranging from the most basic right of survival, to the right for the development of the child's full potential. UNICEF (2011) estimated that 20% of children between the ages of 10 and 14 are child labourers, and as such, children comprise 17% of Nigeria's total labour force. Children have been forced to drop out of school because of their parents' demands in order to boost family income. In addition, Bass (2004:17) observed that the rapid population growth of many less developed countries, high rates of unemployment, inflation, low wages, and deplorable working conditions have contributed to incidents of child labour as children attempt to help support their families. The Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary defines a child as a young person from birth to the age of full physical development. The definitions vary among continents, regions, countries, and states, probably because physical development is reached at different ages. Though the term "child" was not recognized under the Nigerian Constitution, it has been defined by different legislations within the country. Children are easy victims of violence because they are weaker in size, stature, and mental capabilities. (Akwaru, 2010). Child abuse is any act or failure to act on the part of a parent or caregiver, which results in death, serious physical or emotional harm, and sexual abuse or exploitation. (CABT Act 2003) Child abuse can either be sexual or non-sexual. Sexual abuse consists of abuse that can be either child marriage, molestation, or female genital mutilation, while non-sexual

abuse includes child labour, trafficking, kidnapping, and neglect.

Kaduna metropolis is a melting point of different ethnic and religious groups, providing a unique opportunity to study child abuse. Abuse against children is rampant, ranging from forced labour to physical and sexual abuse, although it is largely under-reported. Under-reporting stems from cultural justification of certain forms of sexual abuse associated with cultural practices and the reluctance of children to speak about prior abusive experiences. Fear of their assailants' threats or their parents' reaction may be the cause of this reluctance. In Kaduna State, precisely, over 300 persons were rescued by the police from a rehabilitation school in September 2019. Among those rescued were children, most of whom were between five years of age and under the age of eighteen. The place where these people were housed was tagged "house of torture" as every child there had visible marks of torture on their bodies. Most of them were also chained, and constantly beaten and raped by those who "teach" in the school, thereby violating their fundamental human rights (The Sun, UK 2019). According to a review of 420 police-reported cases of child sexual abuse in Kaduna State, between 2018 and 2021, the majority of victims were females (65.5%), between the ages of 5-14 (70.2%), and familiar with their assailants (71.4%) (Auwal, 2022).

Literature Review**Sexual Abuse and Child Marriages**

Child marriage, the practice of marrying children to adults, is a significant human rights violation, affecting the right to equality, health, education, and personal autonomy (Ogunniran, 2011; UN Children Fund, 2008). Research on child marriage, especially in Nigeria, highlights its negative implications

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for the health and socio-economic development of children, with limited focus on the effectiveness of legal frameworks in curbing this practice.

Female Genital Mutilation (FGM)

Female Genital Mutilation (FGM), which involves the partial or total removal of female genitalia, is condemned globally due to its harmful effects on physical and psychological health (WHO, 1990). The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) mandates states to eliminate practices that harm children's health (UNHR, Article 24). While international conventions have helped raise awareness, their enforcement at the local level remains inconsistent, suggesting a gap in implementation strategies.

Molestation

Molestation refers to forcing or enticing a child into sexual activities, which may or may not involve violence (Kimbrel, 2003). It has severe long-term effects on children, including anxiety, depression, and eating disorders (Moffatt, 2003). This form of abuse, although less publicly discussed compared to others, often leads to long-term psychological damage, which requires further research into therapeutic interventions and preventative measures.

Child Labour

Child labour is defined as work that harms children's safety, health, and development (Betcherman, 2004; ILO, 2002). In Nigeria, children work in sectors such as agriculture, vending, and construction, often under hazardous conditions (Okafor, 2010). While there is legal recognition of the issue, studies on child labour focus mainly on its prevalence without fully exploring the socio-economic drivers or the effectiveness of existing policies in reducing child labour.

Physical Abuse

Physical abuse involves non-accidental harm to children, such as beating or burning, leading to long-term damage (Child Welfare Information Gateway, 2019; Gregory, 2003). Physical abuse often occurs within the family, with children being subjected to degrading conditions under the guise of discipline. Research tends to focus on the immediate effects of physical abuse, but there is a need for more studies on its long-term impact on the development of children and its correlation with other forms of abuse.

Child Rights Act, 2003

The Child Rights Act (CRA) of 2003 was designed to protect children in Nigeria, incorporating international frameworks like the UNCRC (Kamaldeen, 2010; Muhammed, 2009). However, its implementation has been hindered by insufficient political commitment, lack of resources, and weak enforcement mechanisms at the state level, leading to continued violations of children's rights.

Causes of Child Abuse and Child Rights Violations

Child abuse and rights violations result from multiple factors, including poverty, illiteracy, and deficient governance (Betcherman, 2004). Research indicates that economic hardship often forces children into dangerous work, child prostitution, or abandonment (Okafor, 2010). Governance failures, characterized by corruption and inadequate institutional frameworks, exacerbate child abuse, hindering progress in addressing the issue.

Family factors, such as broken homes or harmful cultural practices like early marriage, female genital mutilation, and preference for male children, also contribute to child abuse (Ogunniran, 2011). These practices persist due to a lack of awareness and education, highlighting the need for targeted intervention programs.

Effects of Child Abuse and Child Rights Violations

The consequences of child abuse are far-reaching, affecting the physical, psychological, and socio-economic well-being of children. Health complications, including sexually transmitted infections (STIs) and Vesicular Vaginal Fistula (VVF), are common among victims of child marriage and FGM (WHO, 1990). Abused children also experience psychological crises, such as depression and isolation (Moffatt, 2003). Moreover, they are at an increased risk of engaging in criminal activities, which can perpetuate cycles of poverty and crime, impeding national development (Gregory, 2003).

While much of the literature addresses the prevalence and immediate effects of child abuse, there is limited research on the long-term impact of such abuse on children's life trajectories, particularly in Nigerian contexts. Furthermore, while various international conventions and national laws aim to protect children, enforcement remains weak. A critical gap exists in examining how cultural practices intersect with legal frameworks and hinder child protection efforts. There is also a lack of comprehensive data on the interplay between economic, cultural, and governmental factors contributing to child abuse, which complicates effective policy development. This literature review synthesizes existing studies on child abuse, child marriages, FGM, labour, and related issues, offering insights into the gaps in current research and highlighting the need for more focused investigations, particularly in areas like the enforcement of child protection laws, long-term impacts of abuse, and cultural influences on child rights violations.

Methodology

This study on child abuse in Kaduna metropolis employed a mixed-methods

approach, integrating both qualitative and quantitative techniques to provide a comprehensive understanding of the issue. The aim was to gather in-depth insights into child abuse through interviews, observations, and surveys.

Research Design

A mixed-methods approach was chosen to capture both the personal experiences of child abuse victims and the broader statistical data on its prevalence. Qualitative methods, such as interviews, offered rich insights, while quantitative surveys provided a statistical overview.

Data Collection Methods

Secondary Data Analysis: The researcher reviewed existing literature, laws, and policies relevant to child abuse to identify knowledge gaps.

Primary Data Collection:

Interviews: Conducted with stakeholders, including abused children, Almajiris, staff from correctional homes, NGOs, and government officials, offering both personal and professional perspectives.

Observations: Direct observations of child labour activities were made to identify instances of abuse in public spaces.

Surveys/Questionnaires: A structured questionnaire was distributed to collect quantitative data on child abuse prevalence and forms.

Sampling Strategy

Non-probability convenience/purposive sampling was used, focusing on stakeholders with direct knowledge of or experience with child abuse, such as children from correctional homes, NGOs, and government agencies.

Data Analysis Techniques

Qualitative Data Analysis: Thematic analysis was applied to identify recurring themes and patterns in the interviews, providing a deeper

understanding of the factors contributing to child abuse.

Quantitative Data Analysis: Descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) were used to quantify the types and prevalence of child abuse in the population.

Research Instruments

Interview Protocols: Semi-structured guides ensured consistency while allowing flexibility for in-depth exploration.

Surveys/Questionnaires: Structured to measure child abuse prevalence in the metropolis.

Observation Checklists: Used to document child labour and abuse in public spaces systematically.

Justification for Mixed-Methods Approach

A mixed-methods approach was chosen to explore personal narratives (qualitative) and quantify the extent of child abuse across the population (quantitative). This combination allowed for a holistic view, connecting individual experiences with broader statistical trends, and deepening the understanding of child abuse.

Theoretical Framework: General Strain Theory (GST)

GST was adopted to understand the child abuse phenomenon. It posits that abuse or neglect is a significant strain leading to delinquency (Agnew, 2001). Strains, including economic, social, and emotional stress, contribute to criminal coping behaviours and abusive actions.

Previous studies have shown that abused children are more likely to engage in delinquency and substance abuse, and that caregivers under strain are more likely to engage in abusive behaviour. These strains include:

Economic Strain: Poverty and financial instability.

Social Strain: Social isolation and conflict.

Emotional Strain: Mental health issues and substance abuse.

Results

The prevalence of child abuse in the Kaduna metropolis is increasingly alarming. Its prevalence and kind vary from one locality to another.

An interview with a group of twenty children (Almajiris) of Tudun Wada and Kawo communities also exposes the gap in the full implementation of the Child Rights Act. Children can be seen in their community hawking goods like groundnuts, pepper, pure water, and so on.

Again, an interview with two (2) children at Ahmadu Bello Way, Kaduna, revealed that they serve as aids to beggars who appear to be relatives. And by this earn a means of livelihood where they feed on food bought from roadside food sellers.

Table: The Implications of Child Abuse and Related Findings

Serial	Variable	Number of Respondents	Percentage %
a.	It affects their ability to learn/they may become timid or excessively shy	21	70%(Affirmative)
b.	It increases children’s level of anxiety and fear	21	70%(Affirmative)
c.	It affects their ability to associate with other people or socialize (Abused Children)	19	70%(Affirmative)
d.	Abused children become aggressive and depressed/engage in drug or alcohol abuse(Abused Children)	17	80%(Affirmative)
e.	The high rate of the Child’s Rights Act abuse in Kaduna (Kaduna State Ministry of Human Services and Social Development)	26	70%(Affirmative)
f.	The high rate of conviction of child rights offenders (Kaduna State Ministry of Human Services and Social Development)	20	28%
	Total	124	100

Source: Fieldwork (2021).

Discussion

The study explores the widespread issue of child abuse in Kaduna, focusing primarily on emotional abuse and its profound effects on children. The research draws from interviews with various respondents, including children, abused children, Almajiris (child beggars), staff from correctional homes, NGOs, and government officials. Key findings are categorized into several areas, each addressing different aspects of child abuse and its impact on development.

Key Observations:

Almajiris (Child Beggars)

Almajiris are children who beg on the streets, often in exchange for performing domestic tasks. These children typically do not attend school and are subjected to exploitation. This situation significantly hampers their development and limits opportunities for education and a healthier childhood.

Child Labour and Rights Violations

In communities like Tudun Wada and Kawo, child labour is common, with children

hawking goods on the streets. This practice contradicts the Child Rights Act and restricts children's access to education, further limiting their developmental potential. Additionally, some children assist adult beggars, contributing to their lack of schooling and opportunity.

Abuse and Emotional Maltreatment

Emotional abuse is a significant issue for many children, contributing to psychological distress, low self-esteem, and difficulties in school and social settings. This type of abuse is often inflicted by parents, caregivers, and religious leaders, yet it is frequently overlooked and underreported. The consequences of emotional abuse can be long-lasting, hindering children's growth and development.

Key Variables and Implications:

Impact on Learning and Shyness (Variable A)

Abused children often struggle with cognitive and emotional challenges that disrupt their ability to concentrate and participate in

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educational activities. These challenges can result in withdrawal from class, leading to poor academic performance.

Increase in Anxiety and Fear (Variable B)

Emotional abuse leads to heightened anxiety, fear, and stress, often manifesting as PTSD. These emotional disturbances affect children's social interactions and their ability to form healthy relationships.

Challenges in Socialization (Variable C)

Abused children often face difficulties in trusting others and forming relationships. This lack of social skills can hinder their emotional development and prevent them from building resilience.

Aggression, Depression, and Substance Abuse (Variable D)

The long-term effects of abuse can result in aggression, depression, and substance abuse. As children grow, they may struggle with anger and resort to substances as coping mechanisms, which can have further negative consequences in adulthood.

Abuse of the Child Rights Act in Kaduna (Variable E)

Despite the existence of the Child Rights Act, violations of children's rights remain rampant in Kaduna. This is primarily due to inadequate enforcement of the law, societal apathy, and cultural practices that allow abuse to persist.

Conviction of Child Rights Offenders (Variable F)

The low conviction rate of child rights offenders highlights systemic flaws in law enforcement and the justice system. This lack of accountability prevents the effective protection of children and contributes to the continuation of abuse.

Interpretation in Light of General Strain Theory

General Strain Theory (GST) suggests that individuals who experience emotional or

psychological strain due to unmet goals or stressors may resort to maladaptive coping behaviours. Applying this theory to the findings:

Strain from Abuse and Neglect

Children subjected to emotional abuse experience significant psychological strain, leading to feelings of inadequacy, anxiety, and stress. These emotions may result in maladaptive coping strategies such as withdrawal, aggression, or substance abuse.

Strain from Socioeconomic Factors

Child begging (Almajiris) and child labour are often responses to the socioeconomic strain caused by poverty and a lack of educational opportunities. These children's behaviours are coping mechanisms for their disadvantaged circumstances.

Long-Term Consequences

GST also suggests that prolonged exposure to strain without proper support or coping mechanisms can lead to deviant behaviours in adulthood. This is reflected in the behavioural problems exhibited by abused children, including substance abuse and aggression. Similar studies in Nigeria and internationally have highlighted the widespread violation of child rights, particularly in impoverished areas. In rural and urban slums, children are often forced into street trading or begging, which denies them access to education and developmental opportunities. Countries with stronger child protection laws tend to experience lower rates of abuse and its associated consequences, emphasizing the importance of law enforcement and social services.

Policy Implications:

Strengthening Law Enforcement and Implementation

There is a pressing need to enforce child protection laws, particularly the Child Rights Act. This includes providing resources for law

enforcement agencies to investigate and hold offenders accountable for child abuse.

Public Awareness and Education

Public awareness campaigns should be launched to educate parents, communities, and institutions about children's rights and the dangers of child labour, abuse, and neglect. This can help reduce the social acceptance of child exploitation.

Improved Social Support Systems:

Investment in social services is essential to help abused children. Counselling, rehabilitation programs, and educational support are crucial to addressing the long-term effects of abuse and helping children overcome psychological challenges.

Economic Empowerment for Families:

Addressing the root causes of child begging and labour, such as poverty, requires economic empowerment programs for families. Financial support or skills training for parents could reduce the need for children to engage in exploitative activities like begging or street trading.

Training for Educators and Caregivers:

Teachers, caregivers, and social workers should be trained to recognize the signs of emotional abuse and provide early intervention. Early detection and support can prevent the escalation of abuse and its negative impact on children's development.

Conclusion

Children are the future of any nation, and the way they are treated is a reflection of the country's development. Child abuse is a serious issue that must be tackled promptly to prevent long-term consequences. Various forms of abuse, including child marriages, female genital mutilation, kidnapping, child labour, molestation, neglect, and others, must be eradicated to ensure a safe and healthy environment for children.

In Nigeria, the laws protecting children are ineffective due to several hindrances such as

poverty, cultural attitudes, corruption, and lack of law enforcement. To reduce child abuse, these factors must be addressed alongside enforcing laws that protect children. It is essential to amend any laws that encourage child abuse and ensure they are strictly implemented. Public awareness about child abuse, its consequences, and the importance of law compliance is crucial for safeguarding children's rights.

Recommendations

The research study emphasizes the need for immediate action to address child abuse and neglect, particularly in the Kaduna metropolis. The recommendations presented involve a multi-pronged approach and engagement from various stakeholders to create a safer environment for children. These recommendations are outlined for different groups:

1. Recommendations for Parents

- Sensitize parents on child abuse and discipline: Parents must be made aware of the difference between appropriate discipline and child abuse. Public awareness campaigns can educate parents about what constitutes abuse and when discipline becomes harmful.
- Improve parenting skills: Parenting workshops, seminars, and training programs should be organized to equip parents with non-abusive, effective parenting techniques. Government agencies, NGOs, and religious bodies can collaborate to offer such programs.

These measures aim to address parents' lack of awareness and prevent unintentional harm caused by misguided disciplinary actions.

2. Recommendations for Government

- Full implementation of the Child Rights Act: The government must show political will to fully implement

the Child Rights Act of 2003 and other relevant laws. Violators should be prosecuted effectively.

- Training for law enforcement: Specialized training should be provided to law enforcement officers investigating child abuse cases. This will ensure thorough, effective handling of these cases.
- Regular law reviews: The government should periodically review and update child protection laws to align with international standards and tackle emerging child welfare issues.

These actions will strengthen the legal framework and equip law enforcement with the tools needed to protect children from abuse.

3. Recommendations for Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and Religious Bodies

- Launch child abuse prevention programs: NGOs and religious bodies should collaborate to launch educational and support programs focused on preventing child abuse and providing assistance to abuse victims.
- Provide counselling services: Religious bodies should offer counselling and support to abuse victims within their congregations, ensuring emotional healing and guidance.

These initiatives will provide vital community-based support, offering both preventative education and post-abuse recovery for children and families.

4. Recommendations for Religious Leaders

- Provide counselling and preach against abuse: Religious leaders should offer counselling services focused on preventing child abuse and promoting healthy family dynamics. They should use their platforms to

speak out against abuse in all forms and promote protective attitudes toward children.

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Appendix A

Figure 1: Building housing the victims of child violence

Figure 2: Victims of child violence (Photo source: Sky News, 2019)